

INDUCATION OF DIABETES MODEL IN RATS BY LEAD INTOXICATION AND HIGH FAT DIET

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Annotation: Pathological conditions resulting from the accumulation of heavy metals that enter the body directly or indirectly are of particular interest. In this study, male white mongrel rats weighing 210-220 grams were given water containing 0.05 mg/kg lead salt for 28 weeks and fed a high-fat diet during this time. The amount of glucose in the blood of the animals was checked on the 7th, 14th, 21st and 28th weeks of the experiment. According to his data, it was found that the amount of blood glucose increased by 39.1 per cent in 7 weeks, by 60.7 per cent in 14 weeks, and by almost 2.5 times in 21 weeks. It was observed that by 28 weeks the blood glucose level increased almost 3.5 times, with the index in the control group being 5.2 mmol/l and in the experimental group - 18.2 mmol/l.

Keywords: rat, lead, heavy metals, bile, organism, toxic substances, xenobiotics, type 2 diabetes, environment, blood, glucose, liver, glycogen

Аннотация: Особый интерес представляют патологические состояния, возникающие в результате накопления тяжелых металлов, которые попадают в организм напрямую или опосредованно. В ходе проведенных исследований самцам белых беспородных крыс массой 210–220 граммов в течение 28 недель давали воду с содержанием соли свинца 0,05 мг/кг и в течение этого времени кормили пищей с высоким содержанием жиров. На 7-й, 14-й, 21-й и 28-й неделях эксперимента проверяли количество глюкозы в крови животных. По его данным, установлено, что за 7 недель количество глюкозы в крови увеличивается на 39,1%, за 14 недель — на 60,7%, а за 21 неделю — почти в 2,5 раза. Отмечено, что к 28 неделе уровень глюкозы в крови увеличился почти в 3,5 раза, при этом в контрольной группе показатель составил 5,2 ммоль/л, а в опытной группе – 18,2 ммоль/л.

Ключевые слова: крыса, свинец, тяжелые металлы, желчь, организм, токсичные вещества, ксенобиотики, сахарный диабет 2 типа, окружающая среда, кровь, глюкоза, печень, гликоген.

Аннотация: Оғир металлларни организмга бевосита ёки билвосита йўллар орқали кириб кумуляцияланишидан юзага келаётган патологик ҳолатлар алоҳида эътиборни тортади. Олиб борилган тадқиқотларда 210-220 грами оқ зотсиз эркак каламушларга 0,05 мг/кг кўрғошин тузи 28 хафта давомида сув орқали бериб борилди ва улар шу вақт мобайнида ёғли диетада боқилди. Тажрибани 7, 14, 21 ва 28 хафтадарда ҳайвонларни қонидаги глюкоза миқдори текшириб борилди. Унга кўра қондаги глюкоза миқдори 7 хафтада 39,1 % га, 14 хафтада 60,7% га, 21 хафтада эса деярли 2,5 баробарга ортиши аниқланди. Қондаги глюкоза миқдори 28 хафтага борганда назорат кўрсаткичи 5,2 ммоль/л, тажриба гуруҳиники эса 18,2 ммоль/л ни ташкил қилиб, деярли 3,5 баробарга ортганлиги қайд қилинди.

Калит сўзлар: каламуш, кўрғошин, оғир металллар, саноат, организм, токсик моддалар, ксенобиотиклар, 2-тип диабет, атроф муҳит, қон, глюкоза, жигар, гликоген

Today, special attention is paid to prevention and treatment of pathological conditions arising in nature and living organisms as a result of heavy metal salts entering the environment. Monitoring

carried out in industrialised countries has also shown that their levels in air, soil and water have increased several times. These xenobiotics, along with other changes in ecosystems, have led to changes in the ecological state of soil, water and plants, as well as in the biochemical processes that take place in them. Toxic elements emitted by industrial plants cause changes in the physical and chemical properties of soils used for growing agricultural products [2; 5]. For example, in a study of an area of a mineral processing and metallurgical production centre in southern Spain, levels of As, Sd, Su, Pb and Zn in soil were found to exceed permissible limits [4].

Studies have shown that when examining the composition of drinking water in the Aral Sea region, such elements as Li, B, Mn, Fe, Se, Br, Sr, Ba, Cd, Co, and in agricultural products (wheat, rice and others) such substances as Al, Cr, Fe, Cd, Pb, Ni, Sb exceed the permissible norm several times [1].

Among heavy metals, lead is one of the most toxic. According to the results of recent studies, the emission of lead into the environment as a man-made metal is increasing every year. Lead (Pb) is a chemical element that disrupts the endocrine system in high doses. However, several studies have shown that even low levels of lead have an effect on plasma glucose levels [2].

Exposure to lead has been linked to an increased risk of type 2 diabetes in the population, and research has shown that the two conditions are closely linked. More than 200 results from 60 studies have been published, of which 82 have shown a significant link between toxic substances and type 2 diabetes in the expected direction. In general, it has been found that areas with clean environments and the opportunity to walk in green areas are associated with a lower risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) in the population, whereas areas with increased noise and air pollution are associated with a higher risk of developing the disease [3]. Thus, the results show that there is an organic link in the occurrence of diabetes as a result of increased levels of toxic substances in the environment.

Purpose of the study: The aim of the study was to induce diabetes in animals through lead intoxication and a high-fat diet, and to determine the amount of blood glucose and glycogen in the liver.

Materials and methods: The studies were carried out on more than 50 white rats. Adult male rats were selected for the experiment. The animals were kept in separate cages in clean, bright, ventilated rooms. Five rats were placed in each cage. The cages were made of plastic and had dimensions of 50x30x28 cm. The room temperature was 22-24 °C and relative humidity was 40-60%. The rats received unlimited food and water. The animal feed consisted of: wheat, pistachios, milk and milk products, meat products, wheat bread, greens, vegetables, table salt, cambic food, and animal and vegetable fats. The body weight of adult male rats taken for the experiment was 210-220 g.

Establishment of a model of diabetes. To induce diabetes in experimental animals, they were administered 0.05 mg/kg of lead salt through a probe for 28 weeks, and during this period the animals were fed a high-fat diet. The rats selected for the experiment were divided into 2 groups: Group I - control group (n=7), Group II - experimental group (n=7). Every week of the experiment, blood was taken from the tail of the animals and glucose levels were measured using a glucometer. Intact animals were used as the control group.

Results and discussion. In the studies conducted, rats were given water containing 0.05 mg/kg lead salt for 28 weeks and fed a high fat diet during this time. To determine whether the animals developed a pattern of diabetes, their blood glucose levels were checked at 7, 14, 21 and 28 weeks of the experiment. According to his data, it was found that the amount of glucose in the blood increased by 39.1 per cent at 7 weeks, 60.7 per cent at 14 weeks and almost 2.5 times at 21 weeks. It was observed that by 28 weeks the blood glucose level increased almost 3.5 times, with 5.2 mmol/l in the control group and 18.2 mmol/l in the experimental group.

Conclusion. It can be assumed that air pollution is one of the major risk factors for the increased incidence of diabetes in the population. Epidemiological data are still largely contradictory and have not been systematically evaluated. In this experiment, we have shown that chronic exposure to lead via fatty foods can lead to diabetes. Thus, the increasing incidence of diabetes mellitus in the

population at present indicates that it is directly related to unfavourable environmental factors as well as to factors of poor nutrition.

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